

Potent and selective caspase-2 inhibitor prevents MDM-2 cleavage in reversine-treated colon cancer cells

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Figure S1 Caspases specificity at the P5 position. Human apoptotic caspases (-2, -3, and -8) were screened at the P5 position with the combinatorial fluorogenic substrate library, Ac-P5-Mix-Glu-Mix-Asp-ACC. The relative rate of P5 substrate hydrolysis was divided by the hydrolysis rate of substrates mixtures lacking P5 position (Ac-Mix-Glu-Mix-Asp-ACC, "none = 1") and the specificity profile was expressed as white-red heat map, where the substrates were ordered by caspase-2 preferences, from highest to lowest.

Figure S2 Caspases activation and selected proteins processing pattern in reversine stimulated HCT116 cells in the presence of three inhibitors at various concentrations (0.4 – 40 μ M). HCT-116 cells were pre-incubated with selected inhibitors for 4 hours prior to reversine treatment (24 hours). After this time, cells were harvested, lysed and subjected to SDS-PAGE and Western blotting analysis. Caspase-2 activation was indirectly monitored by the processing of the MDM-2 protein. Results demonstrate that NH-23-C2 is a potent inhibitor of endogenous caspase-2, whereas Ac-23-C2 and zVAD-fmk inhibit caspase-2 much less efficiently.

Figure S3 Caspases activation and selected proteins processing pattern in TRAIL stimulated, apoptotic HCT116 cells in the presence of three inhibitors at various concentrations (0.4 – 40 μ M). HCT-116 cells were pre-incubated with selected inhibitors for 4 hours prior to TRAIL treatment (24 hours). After this time, cells were harvested, lysed and subjected to SDS-PAGE and Western blotting analysis. Caspase-2 activation was indirectly monitored by the processing of the MDM-2 protein. Results demonstrate NH-23-C2 and Ac-23-C2 do not block extrinsic apoptosis even at high concentration, whereas zVAD-fmk block apoptosis very efficiently.

Figure S4 Cross-reactivity and toxicity of NH-23-C2 and Ac-23-C2 inhibitors. Panels A,C The inhibition profiles of Ac-23-C2 (Panel A) and NH-23-C2 (Panel C) towards five cysteine cathepsins (pH 5.5 and 7.2) and proteasome (pH 7.2). Proteases were incubated with inhibitors for 15 min and the residual enzymatic activity was monitored with appropriate fluorogenic substrate. Panels B,D. Toxicity of Ac-23-C2 (Panel B) and NH-23-C2 (Panel D)

Table S1A Structures of the pentapeptide (X-DVAD and X-DEHD) ACC-labeled substrates used for the validation of caspase-2 specificity at the P5 position.

Table S1B Structures of the pentapeptide (V-X-VAD) ACC-labeled substrates used for the validation of caspase-2 specificity at the P4 position.

Table S1C Structures of the pentapeptide (VD-X-AD and VD-X-HD) ACC-labeled substrates used for the validation of caspase-2 specificity at the P3 position.

Table S1D Structures of the pentapeptide (VDV-X-D and VDE-X-D) ACC-labeled substrates used for the validation of caspase-2 specificity at the P2 position.

enzyme	Ac-Val-Asp-Val-Ala-Asp-ACC Ac-VDVAD-ACC			Ac-Idc-hGlu-Thr(Bzl)-Ser-Asp-ACC Ac-WRMP23-ACC			NH-Idc-hGlu-Thr(Bzl)-Ser-Asp-ACC NH-WRMP23-ACC		
	K_M , μM	k_{cat} , s^{-1}	k_{cat}/K_M , $\text{M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$	K_M , μM	k_{cat} , s^{-1}	k_{cat}/K_M , $\text{M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$	K_M , μM	k_{cat} , s^{-1}	k_{cat}/K_M , $\text{M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$
caspase-2	10.9	1.12	102,000	50.6	0.66	12,500	7.63	0.99	130,000
caspase-3	35.3	5.74	163,000	336	0.15	448	331	0.24	731
caspase-8	42.5	0.68	16,000	191	0.23	1,190	167	0.30	1,820
caspase-10	17.3	0.15	8,900	132	0.13	985	81.6	0.31	3,840

Table S2 Kinetic analysis of three fluorogenic substrates: one reference Ac-VDVAD-ACC, and two caspase-2 selective toward four apoptotic caspases (-2, -3, -8, and -10). Caspases-6, and -9 do not hydrolyze any of these substrates.

No.	Structure	[M+H] ⁺ calculated	[M+H] ⁺ measured
ACC SUBSTRATES			
1	Ac-Asp-Val-Ala-Asp-ACC	661.2464	661.2489
2	Ac-Val-Asp-Val-Ala-Asp-ACC	760.3148	760.3221
3	Ac-Idc-Asp-Val-Ala-Asp-ACC	806.2992	806.2995
4	Ac-Arg-Asp-Val-Ala-Asp-ACC	817.3475	817.3455
5	Ac-hCit-Asp-Val-Ala-Asp-ACC	832.3472	832.2451
6	Ac-Tyr-Asp-Val-Ala-Asp-ACC	824.3097	824.3088
7	Ac-Pip-Asp-Val-Ala-Asp-ACC	772.3148	772.3112
8	Ac-DLys-Asp-Val-Ala-Asp-ACC	789.3414	789.3418
9	Ac-Asp-Glu-His-Asp-ACC	757.2424	757.2426
10	Ac-Val-Asp-Glu-His-Asp-ACC	856.3108	856.3109
11	Ac-Idc-Asp-Glu-His-Asp-ACC	902.2951	902.2933
12	Ac-Arg-Asp-Glu-His-Asp-ACC	457.1754 [M+H] ²⁺	457.1823
13	Ac-hCit-Asp-Glu-His-Asp-ACC	928.3432	928.3562
14	Ac-Tyr-Asp-Glu-His-Asp-ACC	920.3057	920.3066
15	Ac-Pip-Asp-Glu-His-Asp-ACC	868.3108	868.3109
16	Ac-DLys-Asp-Glu-His-Asp-ACC	443.1723 [M+H] ²⁺	443.1856
17	Ac-Val-Glu-Val-Ala-Asp-ACC	760.3512	760.3140
18	Ac-Val-hGlu-Val-Ala-Asp-ACC	788.3461	788.3471
19	Ac-Val-Api-Val-Ala-Asp-ACC	802.3618	803.3782
20	Ac-Val-Asu-Val-Ala-Asp-ACC	816.3774	816.3789
21	Ac-Val-Gla-Val-Ala-Asp-ACC	818.3203	818.3205
22	Ac-Val-Asp-Thr-Ala-Asp-ACC	762.2941	762.2951
23	Ac-Val-Asp-Glu(Chx)-Ala-Asp-ACC	872.3672	872.3688
24	Ac-Val-Asp-Thr(Bzl)-Ala-Asp-ACC	852.3410	852.3412
25	Ac-Val-Asp-Thr-His-Asp-ACC	828.3159	828.3169
26	Ac-Val-Asp-Glu(Chx)-His-Asp-ACC	938.3890	938.3881
27	Ac-Val-Asp-Thr(Bzl)-His-Asp-ACC	918.3628	918.3656
28	Ac-Val-Asp-Val-His-Asp-ACC	826.3366	826.3345
29	Ac-Val-Asp-Val-His(Bzl)-Asp-ACC	916.3836	916.3837
30	Ac-Val-Asp-Val-Ser-Asp-ACC	776.3097	776.3088
31	Ac-Val-Asp-Val-Tic-Asp-ACC	848.3461	848.3461
32	Ac-Val-Asp-Glu-Ala-Asp-ACC	790.2890	790.2892
33	Ac-Val-Asp-Glu-Ser-Asp-ACC	806.2839	806.2841
34	Ac-Val-Asp-Glu-Cys(Bzl)-Asp-ACC	912.3080	912.3090
35	Ac-Val-Asp-Glu-Tic-Asp-ACC	878.3203	878.3206
36	Ac-Idc-hGlu-Thr(Bzl)-His-Asp-ACC	992.3785	992.3788
37	Ac-Idc-hGlu-Thr(Bzl)-Ser-Asp-ACC	942.3516	942.3521
38	HN-Idc-hGlu-Thr(Bzl)-Ser-Asp-ACC	900.3410	900.3421
39	Ac-Val-hGlu-Thr(Bzl)-Ser-Asp-ACC	896.3672	896.3651
40	H ₂ N-Val-hGlu-Thr(Bzl)-Ser-Asp-ACC	854.3567	854.3621
41	Ac-Pro-hGlu-Thr(Bzl)-Ser-Asp-ACC	894.3516	894.3507
42	HN-Pro-hGlu-Thr(Bzl)-Ser-Asp-ACC	852.3410	852.3479
43	Ac-Dap-hGlu-Thr(Bzl)-Ser-Asp-ACC	883.3468	883.3536
44	H ₂ N-Dap-hGlu-Thr(Bzl)-Ser-Asp-ACC	841.3363	841.3386
45	Ac-Cit-hGlu-Thr(Bzl)-Ser-Asp-ACC	954.3840	954.3724

46	H ₂ N-Cit-hGlu-Thr(Bzl)-Ser-Asp-ACC	912.3734	912.3697
47	Ac-Tyr-hGlu-Thr(Bzl)-Ser-Asp-ACC	960.3622	960.3500
48	H ₂ N-Tyr-hGlu-Thr(Bzl)-Ser-Asp-ACC	918.3516	918.3471
AOMK INHIBITORS			
49	HN-Idc-hGlu-Thr(Bzl)-Ser-Asp-AOMK	846.3556	846.3565
50	Ac-Idc-hGlu-Thr(Bzl)-Ser-Asp-AOMK	888.3662	888.3668
ACTIVITY BASED PROBES			
51	Biotin-ahx-Idc-hGlu-Thr(Bzl)-Ser-Asp-AOMK	1207.4998 (Na ⁺)	1207.4988(Na ⁺)
52	HN-Idc-hGlu-Lys(Cy5)-Ser-Asp-AOMK	1218.6360	1218.6355

Table S3 Molecular masses of peptide fluorogenic substrates and activity based probes used in this study. ACC-labeled substrates and AOMK inhibitors displayed at least 95% purity, since the activity based probes displayed over 90% of purity.

No	Structure	No	Structure	No	Structure
1	<i>L-Asn</i>				
4	<i>L-Glu</i>				
7	<i>L-Ile</i>				
10	<i>L-Nle</i>				
13	<i>L-Ser</i>				
16	<i>L-Tyr</i>				
19	<i>D-Arg</i>				

22	 <chem>NC(=O)C[C@@H](N)C(=O)O</chem> <i>D</i> -Asn	23	 <chem>OC(=O)C[C@@H](N)C(=O)O</chem> <i>D</i> -Asp	24	 <chem>NC(=O)CC[C@@H](N)C(=O)O</chem> <i>D</i> -Gln
25	 <chem>OC(=O)CC[C@@H](N)C(=O)O</chem> <i>D</i> -Glu	26	 <chem>NC1=CN=C[C@H]1C[C@@H](N)C(=O)O</chem> <i>D</i> -His	27	 <chem>CC(C)C[C@@H](N)C(=O)O</chem> <i>D</i> -Leu
28	 <chem>NCCCC[C@@H](N)C(=O)O</chem> <i>D</i> -Lys	29	 <chem>Nc1ccc(cc1)C[C@@H](N)C(=O)O</chem> <i>D</i> -Phe	30	 <chem>C1CCNC1C(=O)O</chem> <i>D</i> -Pro
31	 <chem>OC[C@@H](N)C(=O)O</chem> <i>D</i> -Ser	32	 <chem>Nc1ccccc1C[C@@H](N)C(=O)O</chem> <i>D</i> -Phg	33	 <chem>CC(O)C[C@@H](N)C(=O)O</chem> <i>D</i> -Thr
34	 <chem>Nc1ccc2c(c1)c[nH]2C[C@@H](N)C(=O)O</chem> <i>D</i> -Trp	35	 <chem>Nc1ccc(O)cc1C[C@@H](N)C(=O)O</chem> <i>D</i> -Tyr	36	 <chem>CC(C)C[C@@H](N)C(=O)O</chem> <i>D</i> -Val
37	 <chem>Nc1ccccc1CC[C@@H](N)C(=O)O</chem> <i>D</i> -hPhe	38	 <chem>NCC(=O)O</chem> β -Ala	39	 <chem>C1CCNC1C(=O)O</chem> <i>L</i> -Aze
40	 <chem>O[C@@H]1CCNC1C(=O)O</chem> <i>L</i> -Hyp	41	 <chem>Nc1ccccc1OC[C@@H]2CCNC2C(=O)O</chem> <i>L</i> -Hyp(Bzl)	42	 <chem>C1CCSC1C(=O)O</chem> <i>L</i> -Thz

43	 <i>L</i> -Pip				
46	 dhLeu				
49	 <i>L</i> -Dab(Z)				
52	 <i>L</i> -Orn				
55	 <i>L</i> -Lys(Ac)				
58	 <i>L</i> -Agb				

61		62		63	
64		65		66	
67		68		69	
70		71		72	
73		74		75	
76		77		78	

79	 <chem>NC(Cc1c(F)c(F)c(F)c(F)c1F)C(=O)O</chem> L-Phe(F ₅)				
82	 <chem>NC(Cc1ccc(Cl)cc1)C(=O)O</chem> L-Phe(4-Cl)				
85	 <chem>NC(Cc1ccc(I)cc1)C(=O)O</chem> L-Phe(4-I)				
88	 <chem>NC(Cc1ccncc1)C(=O)O</chem> L-4-Pal				
91	 <chem>NC(Cc1sc2ccccc2s1)C(=O)O</chem> L-Bta				
94	 <chem>CC(=O)OC(C)C(C)C(=O)O</chem> L-Ser(Ac)				

97	 <i>L</i> -hSer(Bzl)				
100	 <i>L</i> -Cys(4-MeBzl)				
103	 <i>L</i> -Met(O)				
106	 <i>L</i> -Phg				
109	 <i>L</i> -Cha				
112	 <i>L</i> -1-Nal				

115	 H ₂ N OH L-Bpa				
118	 H ₂ N OH L-NptGly				
121	 H ₂ N OH L-Tle				
124	 H ₂ N OH L-Tyr(Bzl)				
127	 H ₂ N OH L-hTyr(Me)				

Table S4 Structure of amino acids used in the caspase-2 P4-P2 screening.

1	 H ₂ N OH L-Cpg				
4	 H ₂ N OH L-Api				
7	 H ₂ N OH L-2-Fal				
10	 H ₂ N OH L-Thyr				
13	 H ₂ N OH 4-Abz				
16	 H ₂ N OH D-Chg				

19	 <i>D</i> -Phe(3-F)				
22	 <i>D</i> -Phe(F ₅)				
25	 <i>D</i> -Phe(4-Cl)				
28	 <i>D</i> -Phe(4-I)				
31	 <i>D</i> -Phe(4-NO ₂)				

34	 <i>D</i> -hPhe				
37	 <i>D</i> -Thr(Bzl)				
40	 <i>D</i> -2-Nal				
43	 <i>D</i> -Dip				
46	 <i>D</i> -Tic				
49	 <i>D</i> -Gla	50			

Table S5 The list of amino acids (in addition to the list from Table 4) that were used for the synthesis of P5 Ac-X-Mix-Glu-Mix-Asp-ACC library synthesis.